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1. Changes with respect to the description of work

No changes to deliverable scope.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is public and will be available at ELEVATE's website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This deliverable reports the activities conducted under Task D.5.3 of the ELEVATE project, focusing on the distributional effects of climate policies, the acceptability of revenue recycling schemes, and the integration of household-level data into Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs). Key findings include:

1. **Mapping Distributional Effects:** We aim to understand how different segments of the population are affected. Traditionally, the literature looks into differences between income groups (e.g. the poorest 20% vs. the richest 20%). Our work shows significant heterogeneity in carbon intensity across households, with horizontal (within-income-group) differences often exceeding vertical (between-income-group) differences. Based on a data-based covering 88 countries we identify which household characteristics (e.g. income, car ownership, cooking fuel use, urban/rural ...) are decisive for households being affected by price-based climate policies.
2. **Acceptability of Revenue Recycling:** A systematic review shows that revenue recycling, particularly green spending (e.g., investments in renewable energy), significantly increases public support for carbon pricing. However, regional differences exist, with Africa, Latin America, and Asia-Pacific showing greater support for green spending compared to North America and Europe. Public preferences emphasize fairness and effectiveness, favouring targeted compensation over universal transfers.
3. **Linking to IAMs:** The integration of household-level data into IAMs highlights the complex interplay between climate policy and inequality. In India, modelled results show that structural change exacerbates inequality more than climate policy, while carbon pricing slows economic transformation. In Brazil and France, climate policies have varying impacts on inequality depending on socioeconomic pathways, underscoring the need for tailored policy design.

Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of nuanced, data-driven approaches to climate policy design, ensuring equity and public acceptance while addressing the diverse impacts on different socioeconomic groups.

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Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	1
2. Mapping Distributional Effects of Climate Policy and Revenue Recycling	3
Introduction.....	3
Distributional impacts of climate policy and effective compensation: Evidence from 88 countries.....	3
Theoretical Framework.....	3
Methods and Data.....	4
Key Results.....	4
Policy Implications.....	8
Outreach and dissemination.....	8
Conclusion.....	9
3. The acceptability of revenue recycling schemes.....	10
3.1. Public support for carbon pricing policies and revenue recycling options: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the survey literature	10
3.2. The role of trusts: Conjoint survey experiments public support for climate policy in the EU (ongoing)	13
3.3. Large-scale household survey on preferences on use of revenue recycling revenues in the EU	13
3.4. Policy Implications and Conclusions	15
4. Linking Distributional Impacts to IAMs.....	16
4.1. Comparing Distributional Effects of Climate Policy and Structural Change in India: The Role of Carbon Pricing in Supporting or Hindering Structural change and Development	16
4.2. Within-country inequality and climate change: Modeling Distributional Impacts	18
4.3. Policy Implications and Conclusions.....	20
References.....	21
Appendix	22

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the activities carried out under Task D.5.3 of the ELEVATE project. The tasks outlined in the proposal are as follows:

- Analyse and map the varying distributional effects of climate policy packages and specific revenue recycling schemes on various groups of the population;
- Evaluate the acceptability of specific revenue recycling schemes in varying countries for vulnerable groups by conducting structured interviews;
- Link distributional impact analyses to integrated assessment models, by using a bottom-up approach (based on household data) to calculate demand-side responses to price and income changes.

In this report, we have organized the content such that the research conducted under each task is detailed in a separate section. Each section summarizes the corresponding working paper, published paper, or ongoing work. Links to full working papers are provided in the Appendix. In the following, we give a quick overview of the structure and main content of this deliverable.

Section 2 investigates the distributional effects of climate policies on households across different income groups and socio-economic backgrounds. It is based on one key study that highlights that within-income-group heterogeneity (horizontal differences) is often greater than between-group heterogeneity (vertical differences), challenging traditional income-based compensation strategies. The study compiles detailed household data of 88 countries and uses multi-regional input/output modeling to determine household specific carbon intensities. Key findings include:

- **Heterogeneity in Carbon Intensity:** Richer households in high-income countries tend to have lower carbon intensity due to access to energy-efficient technologies, while in low-income countries, wealthier households have higher carbon intensity due to reliance on fossil fuels.
- **Determinants of Carbon Intensity:** Factors such as vehicle ownership, urban vs. rural location, and energy use significantly influence household carbon intensity.
- **Compensation Policies:** Uniform lump-sum transfers might be less effective than targeted compensation strategies based on factors like transportation costs, energy use, and location.

This section concludes that income-based compensation policies alone are insufficient to compensate hardship cases and calls for more nuanced, country-specific approaches to address the complexity of climate policy costs.

Section 3: The Acceptability of Revenue Recycling Schemes

Section 3 focuses on the acceptability of revenue recycling schemes, particularly for vulnerable groups. The chapter includes a systematic review and meta-analysis of public support for carbon pricing policies, revealing that:

- **Revenue Recycling Increases Public Support:** Green spending (e.g., investments in renewable energy) significantly boosts public support, while uniform cash transfers and corporate tax cuts have limited impact.
- **Regional Differences:** Studies conducted in countries in Africa, Latin America, and Asia-Pacific generally show greater support for green spending, while those in North America and Europe are more sceptical. Generally there is only little literature in countries beyond Europe and North America.
- **Public Preferences:** Perceived fairness and effectiveness are crucial, with targeted compensation and explicit links to environmental improvements being preferred.

The section also discusses still ongoing primary studies in the EU, including a survey experiment and a large-scale household survey, which further explore public perceptions of revenue recycling schemes.

Section 4: Linking Distributional Impacts to IAMs

Section 4 integrates household-level data into Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) to improve their representation of household impacts. The section includes two studies:

- **India Case Study:** The study contrasts the distributional effects of climate policy and structural change, finding that structural change exacerbates inequality more than climate policy. Carbon pricing slows economic transformation, particularly in the manufacturing sector, but has a smaller regressive effect compared to structural change.
- **Brazil and France Case Study:** The research develops an external inequality module for IAMs, revealing that climate policies have varying impacts on inequality depending on the socioeconomic pathway. The study emphasizes the need for careful policy design to avoid exacerbating existing inequalities.

The chapter concludes that integrating distributional impacts into IAMs is essential for designing equitable climate policies, particularly in the context of economic transformation and structural change.

2. Mapping Distributional Effects of Climate Policy and Revenue Recycling

Introduction

We employed a novel and comprehensive approach to analyse the distributional impacts of climate policies on households, addressing key gaps in existing studies. Unlike prior research that often focuses on single-country analyses or relies on linear models, this study compiles a harmonized dataset of 1.5 million households across 88 countries, statistically representing over 5 billion people. A key innovation is the use of supervised machine learning to examine both vertical (between-income group) and horizontal (within-income group) heterogeneity in carbon intensity of consumption¹. The findings reveal that horizontal differences within income groups within specific countries often exceed vertical differences between them, challenging conventional compensation strategies that primarily target income disparities. By incorporating additional household characteristics—such as vehicle ownership, location, and energy use—the study significantly improves predictions of carbon intensity, demonstrating that income alone is insufficient for designing equitable compensation policies. Furthermore, it identifies clusters of countries with similar patterns of heterogeneity, offering a systematic framework for tailoring compensation measures to specific national contexts. This analysis advances the understanding of how compensation policies can be designed to minimize targeting errors, enhance public support for climate policies, and improve their political feasibility. Below we provide an executive summary of the working paper for this analysis. The [link](#) to the full working paper is available in the appendix.

Distributional impacts of climate policy and effective compensation: Evidence from 88 countries

Theoretical Framework

The study builds on economic and political economy theories related to distributional impacts of policies. It assumes that governments aim to maximize public acceptance when implementing climate policies, balancing efficiency with equity. The framework considers a) Vertical effects (differences in climate policy costs between income groups), b) Horizontal effects (differences within the same income group, often due to household-specific factors such as location, energy use, and transportation choices), and c) Compensation mechanisms, including direct transfers, tax reductions, and subsidies, which can be targeted based on observable household characteristics.

For methodological details please refer to the appendix.

Methods and Data

The research employs a novel dataset combining multiple sources to assess the heterogeneity of climate policy costs at the household level **across 88 countries**, covering more than 1.5 million individual households representing over 5 billion people. The data sources include a) Household Budget Surveys: Provide information on consumption patterns, total expenditures, and socio-economic variables such as education, ethnicity, and household composition b) Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO) Data, which are used to estimate direct (i.e. resulting from burning fossil fuels directly) and indirect (i.e. resulting from specific consumption patterns) carbon intensities associated with different consumption categories across 65 sectors and 160 countries.

A Supervised Machine Learning (Boosted Regression Trees - BRT) is used to analyse non-linear relationships between household characteristics and carbon intensity. We employ K-Means Clustering to group countries based on the key drivers of carbon intensity, helping to identify policy-relevant country clusters.

Key Results

Heterogeneity in Carbon Intensity of Consumption

Figure 1 summarizes the relation between vertical and horizontal effects across countries in the sample. It shows that poor households do not necessarily consume more carbon-intensive goods, that is, results are not necessarily regressive. In high-income countries, wealthier households tend to have lower carbon intensity due to access to energy-efficient technologies. In low-income countries, wealthier households tend to have higher carbon intensity, often due to greater reliance on fossil fuel-based transportation and electricity.

Importantly, we find significant heterogeneity within income groups. Using advanced econometric methods based on supervised machine learning (see appendix for details), we can explain those heterogeneities with household characteristics (e.g. urban/rural, car ownership, etc.). Within-income-group heterogeneity (horizontal differences) is greater than between-group heterogeneity (vertical differences) in most countries.

Figure 1 Vertical and horizontal distribution coefficients. The vertical distribution coefficient (y-axis) compares the median carbon intensity of the richest and poorest quintiles. The horizontal distribution coefficient (x-axis) compares the within-quintile differences (5th to 95th percentiles within quintiles) of the richest and poorest quintiles. Rectangles (A) and (B) indicate higher carbon intensity (at the median) in the poorest quintile compared to the richest quintile; rectangles (C) and (D) indicate lower carbon intensity (at the median) in the poorest quintile compared to the richest quintile. Rectangles (A) and (C) indicate smaller within quintile differences in carbon intensity among the poorest quintile compared to the richest quintile; rectangles (B) and (D) indicate larger within-quintile differences in carbon intensity among the poorest quintile compared to the richest quintile. Point colors indicate GDP per capita for 2018 (inlog-transformed constant 2010 USD).

Determinants of Household Carbon Intensity

One of the most important results from this deliverable is that total household expenditures (income proxy) is an important but insufficient predictor of carbon intensity. Among other significant factors vehicle ownership is a strong predictor of higher carbon intensity, especially in middle-income countries. Further, in some countries the location of the household also matters, urban households have higher carbon intensity, while in others, rural households do (due to reliance on biomass and inefficient fuels). Households using LPG, coal, or kerosene have higher carbon intensity compared to those relying on renewable or informal biomass sources.

Using machine learning we can identify six clusters (A-F) where determinants why households are affected are comparable. While most research has focussed on

developed countries (see e.g. Ohlendorf et al. 2022 for a recent review), we find that most those countries are situated in one cluster (Figures 2, cluster A), where household expenditures indeed a large share of the heterogeneity. Related policy conclusions – e.g. on the design of transfers – might not fit well for countries in other countries (clusters B-F).

Figure 2 shows results for all 88 countries clustered in six clusters. The graphs give information whether vertical distributional effects are progressive or regressive, and they give information on the predictive power of specific household characteristics for a household being highly affected by climate policy.

Figure 2 Feature importance across countries by cluster.

Figure 2.1 Feature importance across countries in Cluster A

Figure 2.2 Feature importance across countries in Cluster B to F

Figure 2.1 and 2.2 shows the importance of features (in normalized average absolute SHAP values) for each country, grouped by country clusters. Blue (red) colors indicate that a feature is relatively less (more) important in a country compared to all other countries and features. 'Sociodemographic' includes features such as household size, gender, self-identified ethnicity, nationality, religion, and language. 'Spatial' includes features such as state, province, district, and urban/rural identifiers. For vertical distribution, blue (red) colors indicate a lower (higher) median carbon intensity in the poorest quintile compared to the richest quintile. For average carbon intensity, blue (red) colors indicate a lower (higher) average carbon intensity across all countries. For goodness of fit (R^2), blue (red) colors indicate a lower (higher) predictive performance compared to other countries. Average carbon intensity and R^2 are not explicitly used for clustering. We assign countries to six clusters using k -means clustering based on scaled feature importance, adjusted for model accuracy. Countries in the same cluster are more similar to each other with respect to factors associated with the heterogeneity in carbon intensity.

Effectiveness of Compensation Policies

Our results hold implications for the design of compensation schemes. If heterogeneity is very large (and not driven by income) it might require targeted, not uniform transfer schemes. Targeted compensation strategies based on factors like transportation costs, household energy use, and location can be more effective than those based solely on income. Those would need to take country-specific characteristics into account. We identify six country clusters with distinct characteristics in terms of carbon intensity distribution, providing a basis for tailoring compensation mechanisms.

Policy Implications

One key implication is that for compensating households for climate policy induced price changes a pure focus on lump sum transfers might fall short. Rather, nuanced compensation policies are needed to address the complexity of climate policy costs and its heterogeneity. In specific countries compensation should also consider factors such as vehicle ownership, energy access, and location.

Outreach and dissemination

Based on the analysis carried out we developed an online tool called the **Carbon Pricing Incidence Calculator (CPIC)** (<https://www.cpic-global.net/>) to analyze the distributional consequences of carbon pricing and various compensation measures across currently 88 countries. The tool calculates the additional costs to households after a carbon price is introduced, i.e. the carbon pricing incidence. The CPIC is intended to provide insights for a broader policy dialogue on design and implementation of carbon pricing schemes. The tool is targeted to a broad audience of societal stakeholders, including policy makers, civil society and media. Supplementing policy analysis, CPIC can help to address socially unbalanced outcomes of carbon pricing. Users can use the CPIC to dive into different scenarios and stylized redistribution mechanisms, and compare the distribution of additional costs in or between different groups of the population in a country. A screenshot of the tool is included below.

Figure 3 Screenshot of the Carbon Price Incidence Calculator. The example used here shows the distributional impact of carbon pricing in Germany for 5 income groups for a carbon price of US\$ 40 / tCO₂ with an equal per capita transfer (lump-sum transfer) compensation mechanism. The calculator can be accessed at www.cpic-global.net

Conclusion

The study provides one of the most extensive cross-country analyses of climate policy distributional effects, highlighting that income-based approaches to compensation may not effectively address disparities in climate policy costs. Instead, targeted, country-specific compensation measures based on household-level characteristics could improve policy acceptance and fairness. The findings underscore the need for data-driven approaches to designing equitable climate policies.

3. The acceptability of revenue recycling schemes

To understand the determinants of public acceptability of various revenue recycling schemes this deliverable provides results of systematic review of public support for carbon pricing policies and revenue recycling options, which has been published in *npj Climate Action*. Below, we provide an executive summary of this article, while the full paper details can be found in the Appendix.

Additionally, two ongoing studies further explore public support for carbon pricing policies and revenue recycling schemes within the EU. The first employs survey experiments in four EU nations (Germany, France, Romania and Spain), while the second is based on a large-scale household survey covering 13 EU countries. A summary of the current progress of these studies is provided below.

3.1. Public support for carbon pricing policies and revenue recycling options: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the survey literature

Introduction

Public support for carbon pricing policies is crucial for their successful implementation. However, opposition to such policies, as seen in protests like the Yellow Vests in France (2018) and fuel price demonstrations in Nigeria (2020) and India (2021), presents a significant challenge. We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of survey-based literature to examine the impact of revenue recycling options on public acceptance of carbon pricing. By synthesizing evidence from 35 studies, 70 surveys, and over 100,000 respondents across 26 countries, the research provides insights into the most effective revenue recycling mechanisms for increasing public support for carbon pricing. The objective of the systematic review was three-fold a) To assess the impact of direct (e.g., carbon taxes) and indirect (e.g., subsidy removals) carbon pricing policies on public support b) To analyze how different revenue recycling options (e.g., cash transfers, tax cuts, green spending) influence public attitudes c) To identify regional variations in support for carbon pricing across different income levels and socio-political contexts.

Methods and Data

The study employed a machine-learning-assisted systematic review and meta-regression analysis to synthesize evidence from multiple survey-based studies. For the systematic literature review, we screened 3,542 studies to identify 35 primary studies covering carbon pricing attitudes. For the survey data analysis we evaluated 70 surveys with 113,356 respondents across 26 countries, conducted between 2005 and 2022. A meta-regression analysis was carried out to assess the statistical relationship between revenue recycling options and changes in public support for carbon pricing. We also

compared responses across North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, Latin America, and Africa to highlight regional differences.

Figure 4 This figure indicates which revenue recycling options are elicited by country and the country as well as regional shares represented in the final sample. In each country, one or more surveys elicited preferences for green spending, and targeted cash transfers, and targeted cash transfers. Surveys in all countries except for Norway and Ecuador elicited for uniform cash transfers. Surveys in all countries except for Norway elicit for tax cuts. Surveys elicit corporate tax cuts in all countries except for Egypt, Norway, Sweden, and Ecuador. Miscellaneous types of revenue recycling options are elicited only in Egypt, India, Indonesia, Spain, Sweden Switzerland, Ecuador, Mexico, and USA. Countries marked in bold and with the check mark are represented in the quantitative analysis. This is because for those countries, our sample includes surveys that provide descriptive statistics and use an unspecified baseline before presenting respondents with revenue recycling options.

Key Findings

The introduction of any form of revenue recycling scheme generally increases public support for carbon pricing (see also Figure 5). However, not all revenue recycling options are equally accepted: The available literature assessed in the systematic review identifies green spending (e.g., investments in renewable energy, public transport, climate projects) to significantly increases support, much more than uniform cash transfers or corporate tax cuts. The study also identifies notable regional differences in public support for various revenue recycling schemes. Countries in Africa, Latin America, and the Asia-Pacific region as well as in Europe generally show greater

increases in support when revenue is used for green spending. Countries in North America and Europe display more scepticism toward recycling revenues lump sum, with smaller effects on public support. Note, however, that the primary study availability in countries of the global South (i.e. in Africa, Latin America or Asia) is very limited. Public finance allocation (using carbon tax revenue for government spending) does not enhance support in any region.

Figure 5 This figure shows the share of positive and negative effect sizes for all regions and individually by each region. a For all surveys included in the quantitative analysis, the share of positive effect sizes is largest for green spending (97%) and lowest for uniform cash (67%). b In the Africa region, all effect sizes for all revenue recycling options are positive, but the sample is small. c In the Asia and Pacific region, effect sizes are positive for public finance (100%) followed by targeted cash transfers (95%). d In the Europe and West Asia region, green spending (100%) is seen very positively, compared to all other options. The lowest positive share is found for uniform cash transfers (64%). e In the Latin America and Caribbean region, all effect sizes are positive for uniform cash transfers, green spending, corporate tax cuts and public finance. The share of positive effect sizes is lowest for tax cuts (75%). f In the North America region, the effect of targeted cash transfers is always positive. For uniform cash transfers, corporate tax cuts and public finance half of the effect sizes are positive (50%), and more than 80% of the effect sizes are positive for green spending and tax cuts.

The interpretation of results requires linking them to other existing literature. For example, it is well understood that perceived fairness plays a key role in the acceptability of climate policies, in particular carbon pricing (Maestre-Andres et al., 2019). In this

regard, our results that people prefer targeted compensation over uniform cash payments might be seen in that light. In a similar vein, people might not necessarily understand the economic principle of carbon pricing to reduce actual emissions. That is, they do not perceive price instruments to be effective per se, but think that revenues are required to foster investments that then are triggering climate mitigation action.

3.2. The role of trusts: Conjoint survey experiments public support for climate policy in the EU (ongoing)

Public support for climate policy is crucial for achieving ambitious emissions reduction targets. However, perceptions of fairness, costs, and institutional trust significantly influence public acceptability. We therefore aim to understand the following: a) Is institutional trust correlated with individuals' beliefs about the impacts of climate policy? b) Can effective communication about climate policy help narrow the gap in policy beliefs between high-trust and low-trust individuals? c) What factors are important to the public when evaluating climate policy options? d) How does improving climate policy based on public preferences influence support for stringent climate measures, such as the EU's Fit-for-55 package?

We are in the process of finalizing a survey experiment, which has involved collecting, harmonizing, and cleaning micro-level survey data from four countries: France, Germany, Romania, and Spain. Using this data we estimate personalized costs of the EU ETS 2, the European-level carbon pricing mechanism for the transport and heating sectors. To support this analysis, we have developed a modelling infrastructure to identify the household characteristics that drive variations in additional carbon pricing costs (based on section 2). Based on this framework, survey participants will receive personalized cost estimates tailored to their sociodemographic information. Additionally, we are designing an information treatment, which will include visualizations of household-specific additional costs, insights into distributional effects within each country and educational materials on climate change and EU climate policy instruments.

With the survey experiment framework in place, the next steps include finalizing the pre-analysis plan and registering it. This will be followed by launching the survey with approximately 12,000 respondents across the four target countries.

3.3. Large-scale household survey on preferences on use of revenue recycling revenues in the EU

We also study the potential role of revenue recycling in a primary study. Revenue recycling has been found to have important implications to reduce or even overturn regressivity of energy expenditures and hence policy costs.

This comprehensive survey investigates public attitudes toward climate change mitigation policies across 13 EU member states. The study collected responses from 19,328 validated participants between June 24 and August 27, 2024, employing an

online survey methodology through a representative panel. The sample was carefully structured to match country-specific demographics across age, gender, and educational attainment, ensuring robust representation of national populations.

The survey focused on public preferences regarding 15 distinct climate change mitigation policies, with respondents indicating their support levels using a Likert scale measurement system. The selected policies were strategically chosen to reflect current policy debates and align with existing EU climate initiatives. The policy set encompassed various governance levels, incorporating both EU-wide and national measures, while spanning multiple sectors including transport, food consumption, and energy.

A particular emphasis was placed on evaluating public reception of key components within the EU's Fit-for-55 package, notably the expansion of emissions trading systems (ETS) into sectors such as agriculture, heating, and transport. The policy selection included both currently implemented measures and proposals under active discussion, providing a comprehensive view of the contemporary climate policy landscape. The research deliberately focused on more stringent policy measures that would require significant behavioral adaptations or financial commitments from citizens, reflecting the understanding that such measures typically yield greater effectiveness compared to softer policy approaches like information campaigns or voluntary initiatives. This survey design enables a nuanced understanding of public acceptance toward transformative climate policies across diverse European contexts, offering valuable insights for policymakers and researchers engaged in climate governance.

Notably, across household income deciles, we find unanimously that poorer households prefer to redistribute revenues, e.g., through a "climate dividend" to vulnerable households or workers affected from the climate transition (bottom two rows in the Figure below). Richer households, on the other hand, on average support the use of revenues to invest in mitigation options such as the expansion of renewable energy.

Figure 6 Support of different revenue recycling schemes across income deciles. Average values across 13 EU countries with 20,056 respondents. Each option (invest in mitigation, invest in adaptation, compensate affected workers, and compensate vulnerable households, was given a priority of between 1 and 4 using a Likert scale.

3.4. Policy Implications and Conclusions

In this deliverable, we highlight the impact of revenue recycling schemes for public acceptability of carbon pricing policies. It is important to note that all revenue recycling schemes increase the acceptability compared to a situation where revenues are generally collected in the public budget.

Looking at both a systematic review and a primary study across 13 European countries implies that green spending is a highly acceptable revenue recycling option. While the existing literature implies it is even the most acceptable one, our primary work implies that there are differences across income groups. This might – on the one hand side – call for policymakers to prioritize climate-related investments to maximize public support. It might, however, also indicate a lack of communication of the key principles of Pigouvian taxation and the resulting behavioural responses. In fact, research not conducted in ELEVATE does confirm the effectiveness of carbon pricing schemes in general (Döbbling-Hildebrandt et al., 2024). Further research might be needed to understand the policy action in this regard.

Confirming previous research, we also find that people support that socially vulnerable groups should receive specific compensation measures to enhance fairness and acceptance. We would like to highlight region-specific differences in the acceptability of measures.

4. Linking Distributional Impacts to IAMs

The final task of Deliverable 5.3 employed a bottom-up approach to integrate household-level data in IAMs to enhance their predictive capacity. To this end, we conducted two studies that follow different methodological approaches. Both studies apply their modeling strategies on case studies. The first study (Leimbach et al. 2024, see appendix for full paper) focuses on India. It contrasts the distributional effects of climate policy with those of structural change in India, investigating whether carbon pricing supports or hinders structural transformation and development. The findings indicate that macroeconomic structural change is likely to exacerbate inequality in India more than climate policy. This study has been published in *Environmental Research Letters*.

The second study (Yu et al., in review) explores the integration of an IAM with an inequality module calibrated to household data, with applications to Brazil and France. A summary of this research is provided below, and a working paper is included in the appendix.

4.1. Comparing Distributional Effects of Climate Policy and Structural Change in India: The Role of Carbon Pricing in Supporting or Hindering Structural change and Development

India is undergoing a significant economic transformation, shifting from an agriculture-based economy to an industry- and service-based economy. This process, known as economic structural change, has profound effects on income distribution. At the same time, India is implementing climate policies, such as carbon pricing, to meet international climate targets. This study examines how structural change and climate policy influence income inequality in India, focusing on whether climate policies hinder economic transformation and whether structural change affects income distribution more than climate policy.

Objectives

The study has three objectives. First, to contrast the distributional effects of structural change and climate policy. Second, to analyze how carbon pricing interacts with economic transformation. Third, to evaluate income and consumption effects on different household income groups in India.

Model Framework

The paper develops a novel modeling framework that integrates IAMs, computable general equilibrium model and micro-level models to analyze the distributional effects of climate policy and economic structural change in India. This is done by soft-coupling several models, including:

- a. The **REMIND model**, a large-scale integrated assessment model (IAM) that handles economic growth and energy system dynamics.
- b. **KITE and JUST trade models**, which simulate international trade and sectoral dynamics.
- c. A **household model** based on detailed income and expenditure data from India, which classifies households into five income quintiles.

The structural change aspect is incorporated by using projections of sectoral shifts, particularly from agriculture to manufacturing and services. These projections are taken from the **Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs)**, which outline various scenarios of economic growth and structural transformation. This structural shift has important distributional consequences because poor households tend to be employed in agriculture, while wealthier households are more likely to be employed in manufacturing and services.

The model then uses these sectoral shifts to calculate the income and expenditure impacts for each quintile of households. Key methods include **income effects and consumption incidences**. Changes in household income due to sectoral wage shifts are tracked and aggregated by income quintile. Changes in the cost of consumption (due to sectoral price changes) are also measured, allowing the analysis of how different income groups are affected by changes in goods and services prices.

Findings

Climate policy (via carbon pricing) has a relatively minor effect on income inequality compared to structural changes, which tend to increase inequality more significantly. Carbon pricing tends to have regressive impacts, hitting the poor hardest, but structural change tends to benefit richer households more as their employment and consumption patterns are aligned with the growing service sector.

A summary of results on the distributional effects can be found in Figure 7, which shows a comparison of a scenario with and without climate policy, compared to a scenario with and without structural change. Results indicate that the distributional effects that need to be expected by baseline effects stemming from economic growth and structural change are severely higher and more regressive than those that can be expected from climate policy until 2030.

Figure 7 Consumption incidence and changes in income across Indian household income groups due to 2 °C climate policy and structural change in 2030. The green lines represent the differences in consumption incidence (panel (a)) and income (panel (b)) in a scenario with climate policy (SSP2-CP2) and a scenario without climate policy (SSP2-Base). The purple lines represent the respective differences between scenarios with (SSP2-Base) and without structural change (NoSC-Base). Negative values indicate that consumption incidence/income values are lower in scenarios with climate policy and structural change, respectively; based on KITE model results.

The impact of climate policy varies with the pace of structural change. Under faster structural transformations (e.g., SSP5), carbon pricing exacerbates inequality due to its greater negative effects on the manufacturing sector, which employs many low-income households.

The paper concludes that supporting structural transformation—by fostering mobility and creating jobs in the manufacturing and service sectors—is a more effective way to address inequality than focusing solely on reducing the effects of climate policy. Climate policies that support the poor through transfers and revenue recycling can be effective but should be combined with strategies for structural transformation to make the poor less dependent on agriculture.

4.2. Within-country inequality and climate change: Modeling Distributional Impacts

This research addresses a critical gap in integrated assessment models (IAMs) by developing an innovative inequality module that enables the analysis of within-country inequality dynamics under different climate change scenarios. The study focuses on Brazil and France as case studies, demonstrating the module's applicability across different socioeconomic contexts.

The research makes significant contributions through the development of an endogenous inequality module based on household deciles, incorporating skill premia, capital income dynamics, and consumption heterogeneity. It provides a comprehensive evaluation of climate policy impacts across income distribution, considering carbon

prices and potential recycling schemes, while accounting for climate impact incidence along income distribution using recent empirical evidence.

The methodology introduces household-level granularity to IAMs by disaggregating populations into deciles and incorporating educational attainment data to model wage differentials. The model accounts for varying returns on capital across income groups and carefully considers consumption patterns, including energy and food expenditures. This detailed approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of how climate policies affect different segments of society.

The research reveals that climate policies have varying impacts on inequality across different socioeconomic pathways (SSPs). In SSP1 (Sustainability) and SSP5 (Fossil-fuel Development) scenarios, stringent climate targets increase inequality by 3-4 Gini points. Other scenarios show slight reductions in inequality (1-2 Gini points) by 2100. Overall inequality projections show significant variation across SSPs, with Gini coefficients ranging from 0.3 to 0.7.

Figure 8: Gini index in Brazil and France, different for different scenarios and policy pathways.

The analysis demonstrates that the relationship between climate policy and inequality is complex and depends strongly on the underlying socioeconomic pathways. The model provides valuable insights for policymakers by highlighting the importance of considering distributional impacts when designing climate policies. These findings emphasize the need for careful design of climate policies to avoid exacerbating existing inequalities, integration of educational and social policies with climate action, and different approaches for emerging versus developed economies.

The underlying dataset has been updated and is freely available at <https://github.com/witch-team/inequality-dataset-for-iams> to be used for future analyses. First data on urban vs. rural and gender is also available. We see clear differences between patterns for urban and rural households. Rural households have higher housing energy expenditures, but lower transportation shares, also due to differences in income and housing sizes. As to the gender dimension, we also have first

results, but we don't find clear differences in energy expenditures across genders. However, we uncover important differences in incomes between the gender and settlement pattern, see Figure 11 for the case of India.

Figure 91: Income inequality, including settlement and gender dimension in India.

4.3. Policy Implications and Conclusions

Through innovative modelling efforts, the two studies in this chapter highlight the importance of extending IAMs to better understand structural changes and distributional effects of climate policy. Together, these studies illustrate that effective climate policy design must account for both macroeconomic structural changes and household-level distributional impacts. The studies highlight that policymakers should integrate climate action with broader development strategies that enhance economic mobility, support vulnerable populations, and align climate goals with social equity objectives. Future research should continue refining IAMs by incorporating additional socioeconomic dimensions, including urban-rural disparities and gender dynamics, to provide even more nuanced insights into climate policy trade-offs and distributional effects.

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Appendix

1. Mapping Distributional Effects of Climate Policy and Revenue Recycling

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2. The acceptability of revenue recycling schemes

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3. Linking Distributional Impacts to IAMs

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Within-country inequality and climate change: Modeling Distributional Impacts- See Working Paper uploaded online at : [Appendix_inequality_MODULE](#)